

Features of the organization of amino acids in the plant-soil system of marsh ecosystems

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Amino acids (AAs) play an important role in the nitrogen cycle in the soil: they are part of humus and play a significant role in the process of soil formation. Soil enrichment with amino acids occurs as a result of the decomposition of plant and animal remains.

Using liquid chromatography, quantitative patterns of formation of bound amino acids in marsh soils of the northern seas of the European north-east of Russia have been established Tidalic Fluvisol (Clayic, Ochric) – White Sea coast; Tidalic Fluvisol (Arenic, Ochric, Epiprotosalic), Tidalic Fluvisol (Loamic, Ochric, Epiprotosalic), Tidalic Fluvisol (Arenic, Ochric) – Barents Sea coast [1]. Additionally, the above-ground part of the biomass of species dominant in the ground cover of coastal tundra ecosystems (cereals, sedges, halophytes) was studied.

Neutral amino acids – glycine, alanine, valine, isoleucine, leucine, proline, serine and threonine, tyrosine and phenylalanine, cysteine and methionine, basic amino acids – aspartic and glutamic acids, and acidic amino acids – lysine, histidine, and arginine – were found in all the studied objects. The fairly uniform qualitative composition of AAs hydrolysates of soils of different origins, humic acids of tundra soils, as well as plants and soil microorganisms, is consistent with literature data [2, 3]. Representatives of the above-ground part of the marsh vegetation contain 90-130 g/kg of hydrolysable amino acids, which make a significant contribution to the total content of carbon (C_{org}) and nitrogen (N_{org}) of the biomass - 10-16 and 50-70%, respectively. The biomaterial of plants in saline habitats is more enriched with protein AAs than in marsh soils. The maximum content of amino compounds is characteristic of the surface horizons of soils, decreasing with depth within the range from 60 to 4.5 mg/kg, which is 8-12 and 30-50% of C_{org} and N_{org} of soils, respectively. The total content of all identified amino acids in the objects of study closely correlates with the content of C_{org} and N_{org} in them ($R^2 = 0.94-0.99$). The results indicate a significant contribution of amino acids to the elemental fund of carbon and, especially, nitrogen in soils and phytomass of coastal Arctic territories.

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